

Fiber-Optic Control of a Time-Steered Millimeter-Wave Transmit Array

David A. Tulchinsky, Paul J. Matthews, Neal Matovelle*, and Christian Hochuli*

Naval Research Laboratory
Code 5651, Optical Sciences Division
*Code 5733, Tactical Electronic Warfare Division
Washington, DC 20375-5338

Abstract

An ultrawideband, fiber-optic, true time-delay, millimeter-wave array transmitter is demonstrated. The beamformer is based on dispersive-prism, optical-delay lines and exhibits squint-free $\pm 60^\circ$ steering in azimuth across the entire Ka (26.5 to 40 GHz) microwave band. This is believed to be the first fully functioning demonstration of a photonically controlled wideband, millimeter-wave transmitter system.

I. Introduction

Phased array antenna systems are increasingly used in a variety of applications due to the many inherent advantages of an electronically steered beam over one with mechanical steering. The advantages include beamsteering speed, reliability, graceful degradation, and long term potential cost reductions. Due to the inherent limitations of traditional all-electronic control over the individual array elements, many of these advantages have not been realized. Some of the major drawbacks have been size, weight, loss, and narrow instantaneous bandwidths [1]. Furthermore, for millimeter-wave arrays, Rotman lenses have been traditionally used for beamsteering. But, due to the difficulties involved with the fabrication, waveguide loss, and dispersion at these frequencies, this approach has not achieved suitable performance over very large bandwidths [2,3].

Numerous photonic architectures have been investigated to address all of these limitations [4,5]. One key advantage of photonic control is its ability

to provide the wideband, true time-delay (TTD) beamforming necessary for many current and future radar applications. Although there have been many successful demonstrations of TTD photonic beamforming at lower frequency ranges (L through Ku bands), most of the techniques are not amenable to wideband millimeter-wave applications due to the stringent time delay resolution (sub-picosecond) and amplitude and phase tracking requirements. For example, switched optical delay lines – which are used in a variety of photonic TTD implementations – would require a path length difference of a few microns in order to achieve the subpicosecond resolution (least significant bit) needed at 40 GHz. In general, the few previously demonstrated photonically-controlled millimeter-wave array transmitters and receivers have exhibited narrow bandwidths or severely limited operationing characteristics due to these difficulties [6,7].

Here, we demonstrate what we believe is the first photonic, ultrawideband, TTD millimeter-wave array transmitter. The technique is an extension of the previously demonstrated dispersive-prism beamformer [8] – further demonstrating the flexibility and utility of this technique. The completed system exhibits $\pm 60^\circ$ azimuthal steering with no observable beam squint over the entire Ka band (26.5 to 40 GHz). It is believed that this photonic dispersive prism approach is viable over a much wider frequency range since the present system's bandwidth is limited solely by the individual antenna array elements, while the beamformer's

bandwidth is limited by the microwave components.

II. System Design

A schematic of the transmit array beamforming system is shown in Fig. 1. The main beamformer, based on the dispersive fiber-optic prism approach, provides a wavelength dependent time delay at each array element, proportional to the position of the corresponding element in the array. This is accomplished by using an optical dispersion gradient across the array. Hence, by tuning the wavelength of the laser the dispersion gradient is translated into a time delay gradient at the antenna element output, producing a time-steered far-field pattern.

An external cavity, wavelength-tunable semiconductor laser with a wavelength range of 1470–1590 nm serves as the optical source for the system. The 1.5 mW output of the laser is amplified to 75 mW by a erbium-doped fiber amplifier (EDFA) and is subsequently modulated by a commercially available 40 GHz traveling wave Mach-Zehnder intensity modulator (MZM). A 0.05 to 50 GHz preamplifier with a nominal gain of 30 dB is used at the RF input of the MZM to overcome the inherently high RF loss in the cables feeding the system and to ensure adequate dynamic range at the MZM.

The modulated optical carrier is then split into four equal parts and fed into the four-channel fiber-optic dispersive prism. The nominal unit length of high dispersion (HD) fiber ($D \sim -93.5 \text{ ps/nm}\cdot\text{km}$) in the prism is 25 meters. The four links thus have 0, 25, 50, and 75 m of HD fiber respectively. The total length of HD fiber in each link of the prism is known to within $\pm 2 \text{ cm}$. The overall link lengths are equalized with dispersion shifted (DS) fiber such that the total difference in the optical time delay between any two links, at the center wavelength (1555 nm), is less than $\pm 2 \text{ ps}$. Final time trimming of

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the fiber optic beamformer.

each link is accomplished by adjustment of each fiber-optic time stretcher. The stretchers have a resolution better than 0.25 ps (3.6 degrees at 40 GHz) and exhibit no microwave phase dispersion across the frequency band. Each fiber-optic link also includes a fiber optic attenuator (FOA) for microwave-frequency independent amplitude matching.

The optical signal is then demodulated by a commercially available 50 GHz p-i-n photodiode (PD) and postamplified by broad band 10 to 40 GHz low-noise amplifiers (LNAs) having nominal gains of $\sim 35 \text{ dB}$. The outputs of the four LNAs are connected to every other element of a 1 x 8 waveguide antenna array. The array is fabricated from thinned WR-28 waveguide with a 4.24 mm element spacing. The unused elements are terminated to reduce unwanted coupling effects between elements.

III. Results and Discussion

After assembly and packaging, the fiber-optic beamforming system was calibrated and tested in the laboratory with a millimeter-wave network analyzer. Several parameters were evaluated to determine if the system met the design

specifications. The fiber optic HD prism was verified to have a uniform wavelength dispersion as well as the correct length of HD fiber to within ± 2 cm in each link. This length error translates into a time dispersion error among the channels of ± 0.02 ps, assuming a wavelength tuning range of ± 10 nm. This extremely small timing/phasing error illustrates the utility of this photonic architecture for millimeter-wave applications.

Figure 2 shows the typical overall system frequency response of the fiber optic beamformer across the Ka band with 1.0 mA of photodiode current. The 10 dB drop off in gain across the frequency range of interest, is typical for the commercial modulator used ($V_{\pi} \approx 35.5$ V at 40 GHz). The system amplitude tracking between the four channels is measured to have a rms deviation of ~ 1.8 dB, while the phase tracking rms deviation is $\sim 8.0^\circ$. These tracking errors, which principally effect the beam steering and beam null formation, are mainly due to the broadband millimeter-wave amplifiers. The overall system gain and dynamic range are limited by the low optical power that is available at the photodetectors and the unavailability of a more efficient MZM in the frequency range of interest.

The antenna array and fiber optic beamformer were also tested in a compact anechoic millimeter-wave radar range. A network analyzer was used to drive the RF input of the system. The radiation from the transmit array was focused onto the receive antenna by an off-axis parabolic microwave mirror. Azimuthal scans were taken across a $\pm 70^\circ$ range in 0.25° increments, at frequencies ranging from 26.5 to 40 GHz in 0.5 GHz increments. The frequency scans were limited on the low frequency end by the cutoff frequency of the WR-28 waveguide ($f_c \approx 21$ GHz) and on the high frequency end by the roll off (~ 40 GHz) of the millimeter-wave postamplifiers.

Fig. 2. Frequency response of one of the links in the millimeter wave beamformer.

Two examples of measured antenna patterns are shown in Fig. 3(a) and 3(b) which are intensity plots of the transmitted radiation as a function of azimuth and frequency. The images have been normalized for the frequency response of the system but not the antenna element pattern of the array. With the laser tuned to 1555.0 nm [Fig. 3(a)] and 1564.2 nm [Fig. 3(b)] the expected steering angle is 0° and -45° respectively. The main lobe is readily discernable at the expected steered angle and exhibits squint free operation over the full 26.5 to 40 GHz frequency range. The first grating lobe, calculated to be $\sim \pm 60^\circ$ away from the main beam at 40 GHz is clearly visible in both plots. The two expected side lobes are visible on either side of the main beam. The degradation from ideal of the measured intensity patterns is believed to be due to the amplitude and phase tracking errors in the microwave components in the system. The main beam was also steered to several angles between $+60^\circ$ and -60° yielding similar squint free results over the tested frequency band.

IV. Conclusions

We have developed and demonstrated a ultrawideband beamformer for millimeter-wave transmit arrays. The system is based on the fiber-optic dispersive prism architecture using only commercially available components.

Fig. 3. Array pattern intensity plots as a function of mechanical angle and frequency with the laser adjusted for (a) broadside radiation ($\lambda = 1555.0$ nm) and (b) optical steering to -45° azimuth ($\lambda = 1564.2$ nm).

The beamformer was characterized for microwave signal losses, dynamic range, and amplitude and phase tracking errors. Additionally, it was used to drive every other element of a 1×8 waveguide array, and steered antenna patterns were measured in an anechoic chamber. The system demonstrated squint-free array steering across a $\pm 60^\circ$ azimuthal span and over the entire Ka (26.5 – 40 GHz) frequency band. We believe this to be the first demonstration of an ultrawideband true time-delay, photonically steered millimeter-wave transmit array.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Office of Naval Research.

References

- [1] R. C. Hansen, *Phased Array Antennas*, (New York, John Wiley & Sons, 1998).
- [2] Y. M. Tao, G. Y. Delise, "Lens-fed multiple beam array for millimeter wave indoor communications", *IEEE Antennas and Propagation Society International Symposium Technical Digest*, vol. 4, pp. 2206-2209, 1997.
- [3] E. O. Raush, A. F. Peterson, W. Wiebach, "Electronically scanned millimeter wave antenna using a Rotman lens", *RADAR '97*, pp. 374-378, 1997.
- [4] H. Zmuda and E. N. Toughlian, *Photonic Aspects of Modern Radar*. (Boston, MA, Artech House, 1994).
- [5] Selected Papers on Photonic Control Systems for Phased Array Antennas, N. A. Riza ed., *SPIE Milestone Series*, vol. MS 136, 1997.
- [6] L. L. S. Huang, C. H. Lee, H. L. A. Hung, "Optically controlled generation and true-time-delay phase shifts of broad-band 60 GHz signals," *IEEE Microwave and Guided Wave Letters*, vol. 3, pp. 42-44, 1993.
- [7] V. A. Manasson, L. S. Sadovnik, V. A. Yepishin, "An optically controlled MMW beam-steering antenna based on a novel architecture", *IEEE Trans. on Microwave Theory and Tech.*, vol. 45, pp. 1497–1500, 1997.
- [8] R. D. Esman, M. Y. Frankel, J. L. Dexter, L. Goldberg, M. G. Parent, D. Stilwell, D. G. Cooper, "Fiber-optic prism true time-delay antenna feed", *IEEE Photon. Technol. Lett.*, vol. 5, pp. 1347-1349, 1993.